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Analysis of the significantly improved results after the implementation of a major pedagogic reform in an engineering degree programme

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ABSTRACT

All the engineering curricula of the Metropolia University of Applied Sciences were renovated in 2014. The teaching and learning has since been based on larger course entities and collaborative pedagogy. The most thorough reform was conducted in the department of electrical engineering where all the courses are now organized in 15 ECTS entities, which are given by a larger number of professors integrating their subjects and assessing the course with one single grade. It has been already previously shown that the reform is extremely successful with respect to student progression and drop-out rate, and the improvement has been much more significant in this department compared to the other engineering departments making only minor pedagogical changes. A student feedback survey was completed in 2017 and the student satisfaction has been greatly improved in the student groups following the new curriculum. The first group of these students graduated after the spring term of 2018. Previously only 40% of the graduates graduated in due time (60% later). Due to the modular structure of the curriculum as well as other key elements of the new pedagogy the programme made its record ever in the number of graduates in 2018 (67% in due time or earlier; 33% later). The drop-out rate is as well significantly improved (decreased). This paper presents the new pedagogy, the significantly improved metrics as well as the actual process of implementing a revolutionary pedagogic paradigm shift in an engineering degree programme discussing as well the major challenges of the implementation

1 INTRODUCTION

Traditionally one of the common challenges in the engineering degree programmes of the Finnish Universities of Applied Sciences (UAS) has been the high drop out rate as well as the students' slow progression in their studies. In 2014 the Finnish ministry of

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education decided to base the funding of the universities on two key factors: the number of graduates as well as the number of students completing more than 55 ECTS yearly (of nominal 60 credits). Before the implementation of the new funding scheme only 30 - 40% B. Eng graduates completed their studies in the nominal 4 years (8 semesters). *Fig.1* shows the percentages of the graduates of the degree programme in Electrical Engineering and Automation Technology (EE) of Metropolia UAS of four consecutive years of intake. In 2015 40% of the graduates (year of intake 2011) got their degree in due time and this result was the second best of the engineering programmes of the university. The results were improved for student groups starting in 2012 and 2013 because by then the new funding scheme was published and minor steps of improvement were taken. As seen in *Fig. 1* the results were significantly improved for the 2014 group (graduation in 2018). This is due to the new pedagogical methods and the modular curriculum implemented in 2014. This paper discusses the methods of the pedagogical reform and shows the results in detail. The improvement is significantly better in this programme compared to the other engineering degree programmes of the university due to the more thorough implementation of the pedagogical reform.

Fig. 1. The percentage of the graduations in nominal time in the degree programme in Electrical Engineering and Automation Technology for four consecutive years.

1.1 The degree programmes and study groups

The EE programme is the second largest engineering degree programme in Metropolia UAS having a yearly intake of 160 full-time (daytime) engineering students as well as 50 part-time students. The nominal duration of studies is four years (8 semesters) in both cases. The same department runs as well a parallel programme in electronics in which tuition is completely in English as well as a post-graduate program with a yearly intake of 30 students. The English electronics programme and the post-graduate programme are not included in the analyses because their results may not

be clearly compared to other degree programmes of the university. The results of the electronics programme have been as well analysed and the trend is similar to the results presented here but a detailed analysis of the post-graduate programme is still to be done.

1.2 Different approaches for improvement

Before 2014 all the engineering curricula of the university were based on relatively small courses (typically 3 ECTS) and one of the main reasons for the poor metrics was the traditional way of organizing lots of small theoretical courses of mathematics and physics in the beginning of the studies thus increasing the number of drop-outs during the first four semesters and forcing the students to retake these courses over and over again during the final years complicating the completion of the professional studies and thus prolonging the graduation. During the curriculum design process in 2013-2014 it was decided on university level that the size of each individual course should be at least 5 ECTS and in the field of engineering a specific package of basic mathematics and physics was specified for all the engineering programmes. The size of that package is only 10 ECTS and different programmes may then increase the amount if needed. It was as well suggested that the basic studies should be integrated more deeply to professional studies to focus on the applications of these studies to practical engineering subjects instead of pure theory.

Fig. 2. The amount of compulsory mathematics and physics in eight different engineering programmes after the curriculum reform.

Different programmes chose different approaches to improve their metrics and some programmes did reduce the amount of these difficult subjects to minimum while some programmes such as the EE and electronics programmes chose a completely another perspective by having the amount of these subjects at the same level as before by integrating the contents. *Fig. 2* shows the amount of compulsory mathematics and

physics in 8 different degree programmes of the university after the curriculum reform of 2014.

2 THE REFORM

2.1 Course integration and modular curriculum

A more detailed description of the modular structure of the curriculum on the degree programme in Electrical Engineering and Automation Technology is found in [1], [2] and [3]. The curriculum is based on courses of 15 ECTS in which different contents are integrated. One such course is given by three to five different teachers who plan, organize and assess the course together. The duration of one such course is typically 8-10 weeks covering one study period (each semester is divided to two consecutive periods). Only one single grade is given for one course and all the courses are based on continuous assessment (i.e. different tasks for students to be completed throughout the course and assessment as well as feedback of these tasks given instantly).

The first year of study consists of four consecutive courses compulsory for all the students in the EE programme and the four consecutive modules of the second year are major specific (at this stage one of the majors is merged to the parallel electronics programme). The last two years consist of optional modules, some electives, internship periods, the innovation project and the thesis project. The students find the modular structure very clear and the student feedback of the model has been very good otherwise as well [4]. According to the feedback survey of the graduating students in 2018 the electronics programme is ranked as #1 of the engineering programmes of the university and the EE programme as one of the best as well.

2.2 Initial implementation and first results

The new curriculum was launched for the first year students in late August 2014. The teachers for the first year courses were carefully selected among the most cooperative staff members and different methods to integrate the contents and different assessment schemes were encouraged. All our teachers have completed a compulsory pedagogical training and thus most of them are able to adjust well to new methods of teaching. After the first semester the student progression was analysed [2] and the best integration and assessment practices were selected. The content integration of the first year courses is more difficult (physics, maths, professional studies, programming, communications, etc.) compared to the more subject specific courses later. The results were however very encouraging and it was then easier to motivate all the academic staff members to apply this model.

The results after two semester did show [2] that more than 80% of the first year students were able to complete all their compulsory first year studies (previously 40 - 50% only). A similar analysis was just completed for the first year students of the academic year 2017-18 and those results may be seen in *Fig. 3*. This graph shows the percentage of the first year students of five different engineering programmes completing all the compulsory first year studies in due time. The large difference between the EE programme (86%) and the others may be explained by two benefits

of the integration: 1) the students are basically “forced” to complete all the subjects in due time, otherwise they would fail a larger course entity, 2) in other programmes the courses of mathematics and physics are still mostly organized traditionally and their failure rate remains too high.

Fig. 3. The percentage of students completing all first year courses in due time in five different engineering programmes (academic year 2017 - 18).

2.3 Challenges

The number of academic staff members teaching in the degree programme is approximately 30. During the first year of implementation (academic year 2014 - 15) only 40% of them were teaching the first year students according to the new model. The feedback from these staff members was generally very positive even though they faced many transition phase problems in accreditation of prior learning, finding suitable platforms for common assessment etc. After the second year of implementation most teachers and after the third year all the teachers were involved. The results of the employee satisfaction survey in 2017 (the third year of implementation) were much worse than expected and the reasons may be tracked to the implementation of the collaborative pedagogy, the course integration and the continuous assessment in the new model.

Some staff members are more willing than others to design common tasks, share materials and cooperate otherwise with their colleagues and that is quite understandable. Some teachers also heavily criticized the continuous assessment schemes preferring to give only larger exams at the end of the course after which they have four weeks for assessment. Many teachers also did complain about the fact that in some cases students may compensate their lack of knowledge of certain difficult subjects by their knowledge (and points) from some other not so difficult subjects within the same course. These topics are still constantly discussed and some staff members still have problems in following the common rules of assessment etc., which then leads to student complaints. The main points of criticism (of some professors) (together with the authors' comments are listed below:

- all the study material delivered to the students is open to all other teachers of the module (true; some teachers avoided this by using external moodle-pages)
- continuous assessment finally leads to more assessment work by the teachers (partly true, but improved pass-rates minimizes the resit work)
- the assessment schedule is more strict (true, but generally the students should always have feedback of their learning asap, not many weeks after the final exams only)
- within one module the students may compensate the tasks of the “difficult” subjects by the tasks of the “easy” subjects (partly true; our analysis shows that there’s only a few cases of such behaviour; this is as well the case in more traditional assessment since in order to pass a large end exam the students may collect points from the easy problems of the exam without being able to complete the most difficult ones)
- some colleagues do not perform well enough or work hard enough in teaching the modules (true; that’s however the case as well if the teachers give separate courses; here it’s at least visible; unfortunately some people do not want to cooperate with some of the others; in the academic world these problems are very difficult to solve)

To overcome these challenges the assessment requirements are now made more flexible for the teachers. Also minimum pass level of each topic within a course were introduced. This is quite an unfortunate compromise because after these adjustments the actual integration of different topics is more difficult. However fortunately still today most teacher groups do follow the original guidelines. The teachers of the basic studies (maths, physics, languages etc.) are the most willing to follow them as well as all the teachers of one of the three majors. On the other hand one of the majors totally abandoned this scheme and will be organizing all their courses of the last 6 semesters on 5 ECTS non-integrated course basis.

3 THE RESULTS

The first student group started their studies according to this curriculum in autumn 2014 and their nominal graduation date was in May - June 2018. After that it has been possible to analyse the graduation percentages as well as the drop-out rates of the first student group. The nominal time graduation percentages as well as the drop-out rates for both the full-time and part-time students are presented in the graphs below for five consecutive years of intake (nominal graduation 4 years later).

Two versions of drop out-rates are calculated and both versions are also taken into account in the calculations of the graduation percentages. In version 1 the drop-outs with no credits completed are not included in the drop-out rate. The reason for this is that in the total number of drop-outs (from the university statistics) also the accepted students who did not even start their studies are included. However in this case there might be some students excluded who had tried their best without any success. Such

students should be included in the analysis, thus the truth lies somewhere between the two versions.

3.1 Graduation percentages

The percentage of full-time students graduating in nominal time of 4 years is presented in *Fig. 4* and the same percentage of the part-time students in *Fig. 5*. It may be seen that these metrics have improved by approximately 20 percentage points after the implementation of the new curriculum. As expected the percentages of the part-time students are lower than that of the full-time students (and the drop-out rates are higher correspondingly) due to the fact that the part-time students tend to prolong the studies even though all their project courses etc. are directly linked to their work and their prior learning is accredited in the beginning of their studies.

Fig. 4. The percentage of full-time students graduating in nominal time of 4 years (version 1: drop-outs with no credits completed not taken into account)

Fig. 5. The percentage of part-time students graduating in nominal time of 4 years (version 1: drop-outs with no credits completed not taken into account)

3.2 Drop-out rate

The drop-out rate of the full-time students is presented in *Fig. 6* and the drop-out rate of the part-time students in *Fig. 7*. It can be seen that the drop-out rates for all the students before the implementation of the new curriculum have been alarmingly high. It may as well be seen that the implementation of the new model has been improving (decreasing) the drop-out rate significantly. It has to be admitted that the drop-out rate for the part-time student group graduated in 2018 (intake 2014) is somewhat too optimistic, because there is still active students in the group and a significant number of part-time students tend to drop out after 10 semesters (one additional year after the nominal 4 years is automatically given).

Fig. 6. The drop-out rate of full-time students
(version 1: drop-outs with no credits completed not taken into account)

Fig. 7. The drop-out rate of part-time students
(version 1: drop-outs with no credits completed not taken into account)

3.3 Comparison to other degree programmes

Fig. 8 and *Fig. 9* show some comparisons between different degree programmes of the intakes of year 2015. This data is from April 2019 when the students are just completing their eight semester before their nominal graduation date. *Fig. 8* shows the averages of the credits completed by the eight semester students in different degree programmes and *Fig. 9* shows the drop-out rates of the same students thus far. Only full-time students are taken into account in these analyses and all the drop-outs are included in the drop-out rate (as version 2 in *Figs. 4-7*).

The data presented in Fig.8 is somewhat less reliable, since the students are still completing their last courses and some students already have their final year projects registered and some do not. However the trend is very much the same as in *Fig. 3* where only the five first programmes are analysed.

It is clear that many other engineering degree programmes have as well improved their results after the curriculum reform in 2014. This is very good news and the EE programme does not even rank as #1 in neither of these metrics. However the overall improvement is best in this programme and these results are achieved without reducing the amount of the basic studies as can be seen in *Fig. 2*.

Fig. 8. The average of the ECTS credits of students in their 8th semester (8 engineering programmes; year of intake 2015)

Fig. 9. The drop-out rate after 8 semesters in eight engineering programmes (year of intake 2015)

4 CONCLUSIONS

The implementation of the new curriculum based on collaborative learning, modular structure, continuous assessment and course integration in the degree programme in Electrical Engineering and Automation Technology in Metropolia UAS has significantly improved the most important metrics of the programme (student progression, drop-out rate, etc.). Additionally it also has a positive impact on the funding of the programme.

Besides these analyses the student feedback of the first student group has been analysed in two occasions, during the second year [2] and after graduation. The student feedback of the new model is very positive. The degree level learning outcomes of the graduates has not been analysed at all. Many teachers have compared the learning outcomes of their subjects to previous years by organizing larger tests within the new courses and the result are positive since in the continuous assessment scheme in the new model encourages student activity throughout the courses instead of focusing on larger end exams only.

The student feedback has been very good but it has been relatively difficult to implement the model completely because some academic team members have felt that they have lost some of their academic freedom by following detailed assessment system and deadlines. Therefore some basic guidelines of the model have been made more flexible in order to be suitable for all staff members. This however makes the implementation of the model more difficult. Most academic staff members are very satisfied with the model but currently some courses (within one major of the EE programme) are already being transformed to the old traditional way of teaching and learning.

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